

Implementing Aggregator Normalization Form for Databases

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ABSTRACT

We give the definition of the aggregator normalization form of data in a database.

Keywords: database, normalization form, aggregator.

INTRODUCTION

Database normalization forms is a way of representing it in a more complex and reliable way [1, 2, 3, 4], recently the new normalization form was introduced [5] based upon the set of input data. We present the data which could be aggregated according to the function in a row.

AGGREGATOR NORMALIZATION

We define the set of aggregator functions for the row r as:

$$F = \{f : r \rightarrow R\}.$$

According to this function we aggregate the sum, production or any other operating according to function the set of functions G :

$$G = \{t \in T : g_f(t) = g_t(f(r))\},$$

where T is a set of tables where the row is to be aggregated and, thus, represent the final normalized form according to statistical computation.

CONCLUSION

We have defined the new way of representing data according to aggregator normalization form, which is designed in order to store final data as a single row for the defined list of facts in data.

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